

Herdsmen/Farmers Conflict, National Security And Development In Benue State, 2014-2024

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the complex relationship between herdsmen/farmers conflicts, national security, and the Eco-Violence Theory in Benue State, Nigeria, spanning from 2014 to 2024. It investigates the root causes of these conflicts, exploring environmental factors, resource scarcity, and the impact of these issues on both communities and the broader national security landscape. Utilizing the Eco-Violence Theory as a framework, the research analyzes how environmental degradation and competition for resources exacerbate tensions and contribute to violence. The study will assess the socioeconomic and political ramifications of the conflicts, including displacement, loss of life, and erosion of social cohesion. Furthermore, it evaluates the effectiveness of governmental and non-governmental interventions aimed at mitigating the conflicts and promoting sustainable solutions. The research aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to address this critical issue.

Keywords: Herdsmen-Farmers Conflict, National Security, Benue State, Eco-Violence Theory, Resource Scarcity, Conflict Resolution, Environmental Degradation

INTRODUCTION

Farmers and herders have long history of relationship and co-habitation in West Africa and Nigeria inclusive. Their differences have also lived with and among them over these years. The case of herds grazing on the farm of the farmers, and the farmer killing the cattle's of the herders for grazing the farmer's crops, with minimal physical reactions was uncommon, until most recent times. Recently, there has been a massive upsurge in the cases of conflict and violent clash in Nigeria between the farmers and the herders. The farmers and herders have a long tradition and commercial relationship; though there have being skirmishes of disparity existing between them, that were usually and effortlessly resolved by the two groups peacefully. (Nzeh, 2015; Goke, 2018). Olanijan et al, 2015, Olayoku, 2014, Okeke, 2014, state that there has been an upsurge on the numbers of conflicts between farmers and herders in Nigeria recently. The relationship between the agricultural farmers and the cattle rearers had been cordial and stable, which had enable them work side by side each other. According to (Shettima and Tar, 2008. 163) the agricultural farmers and the pastoralist have along heritage and economic relationship, though there were sources of disagreement between them that have always been resolved peacefully.

The relationship between the agricultural farmers and the herders is more or less symbiotic, as the herds graze the farm and in-turn dumps their dung's or dairy product as protein and manure needed by the farmer to fertilize the crops and fields. To corroborate this, Monod, (2018) noted that the survival of the

pastoralist group is formed under interaction with sedentary farmers. This, it becomes apparent that the interdependent linkage flows as each group needs water, land, fodder and other land use for their economic activities. Sadly, this cordial and mutually beneficial relationship that has existed centuries ago has been bastardised with many armed conflict arising from this area, snowballing into widespread violence, death, destruction of properties, and displacement of the inhabitants.

As it were, there are plethora of reasons advanced by various scholars for the collapse of long symbiotic and cordial relationship that had existed between the farmers and herders in Nigeria, and Benue State precisely. Some are of the view that, the breakdown of the farmers and herders good commercial relationship is a result of environmental degradation (Hellstrom, 2001, Niemela et al, 2005) climatic change in irregular and low rainfall that has placed constraints in grassland and grazing movement potentials, and crop production (Ifatimehin, 2008) cattle rustling (Okoli and Okpaleke, 2014, Olaniyan et al, 2-015) property rights (Beger, 2003), explosive population growth resulting to fierce rivalry for land and space (Adisa, 2012, Olabode & Ajibade, 2010) and the globalization of the economy.

Much as many scholars and researchers hold firmly the view that the increasing conflict between this two groups is connected to the activities of the pastoralist uncontrollable quest for grazing fields for their cattle's deliberating or unintentionally destroy the field and crops of the farmers, as well as the cattle rustling and killing by the farmers on the other hand. It is obviously not enough to stir the height of animosity and hatred leading to the incessant conflict between the farmers and herders, because all these factors and reasons had been there.

It is on the basis of the foregoing views regarding the frequent trends of farmers and herders conflict in Nigeria and Benue state in particular that proposing this study is very imperative and timely to have a better grasp of the continuous and increasing farmers and herder conflict. It will be practically difficult to have this study cover every part of Nigeria, as there is no region without an experience of the farmers and herders armed violence within the shortest period of this study. The study is therefore focused on Benue state (The food Basket of the Nation), which in the opinion of many is the hot bed of the farmer/herder conflict.

Statement of Problem

The intermittent occurrence of farmers and herders conflict is not a new trend in Nigeria, most commonly in Benue state. Regrettably, what is novel is the spate, the regularity and the number of properties destroyed and lives lost across Benue state. Again, there are a plethora of analysis by various scholars on the causes of the farmers and herders conflict, as well as the escalation of violence within the period under review. Some attributed the conflict to the scarcity of natural resources exacerbated by competition over the meager resources available (Donald and Jo-Ansie, 2010) cited in Anastasia. S.S, (2018). Idowu, (2017) noted that, while the Fulani herdsmen maintained that, they are free to move around the country because of their right for free movement, the farmers see this movement most especially when such movement is into their farmlands as invasion and infringement on their communal and personal properties inherited from their grandparents.

Some argued that climate change (desertification) puts pressure on the herders from far north to migrate to other areas in search of grazing land. Although, the minority Fulani settlers and the indigenes and Benue people had lived a relatively cordial relationship and more especially the sedentary or the agricultural farmers and the pastoral herders (Osaghae & Suberu, 2005, Gengi 2014).

Regrettably, it appears that there is no agreement among scholars as to the causes of the recent and destructive violent conflicts between Fulani herders and the farming population and communities in Nigeria and particularly Benue state. Again, the various argument held and adumbrated above have not reasonably facilitated the Nigerian state in any meaningful way, addressing this, hydra-headed problem. This is because any attempt for the government to approach the problem from a specific way will not only be a narrow approach to the solution but also underplaying possible alternatives that can be adopted in solving the problem. A known example was the government passage of a bill in the parliament that seeks to establish grazing reserves or routes across all the states of the federation. This kind of approach suggests that the Nigerian government has accepted the climate change narratives as the principal actor

responsible for the escalation in conflicts between the Fulani herders and the agricultural farmers in the country (Okeke, 2014). This position has practically been opposed by scholars such as Okeke(2014), who maintained that such approach by the government would exacerbate the conflict between the herders and the farmers, because the government decision to establish grazing reserves will involve the dispossession of farmers and landowners from their land, they consider as an ancestral inheritance.

However, whatever be the case, the migration of herders down other parts of the country from their traditional abodes, competition over scarce resources, climate change (desertification) explosion in population of human beings and cattle, cattle rustling and more are in the words of Moritz (2010) structural conditions. It's problematic as the farmers and landowners would rather die protecting their inheritance from their forebears', while the herders have adopted more and maximum violent mechanism in securing grazing lands for their cattles. This has resulted to the proliferation of small arms and light weapons in which case herders are seen parading and leading their herds carrying AK 47, machetes and other weapons. The farmers and communities on the other hand have not also folded their hands to watch their sources of livelihood destroyed, and as a result have recruited various nomenclatures of local vigilantes to protect their farm lands and their communities. As a case, the situation degenerates as the herders and farmers continue to cause havoc to the communities, endangering the lives and properties of the innocent people (Genyi, 2014) quoted in Anastasia, (2018)

As the Nigerian government has shown bereft of ideas and the abilities to resolving the conflict to instill perpetual peace in various communities bedeviled with the herders and farmers related conflict considering the attendant significant loss and destruction of lives and properties. It becomes only germane to critically study the impact and implications of this conflict on national security and particularly the security of lives and properties in Benue state to forestall future conflict.

The aim of this study will be to determine the causes of the recent and incessant conflict between herders and farmers and its implications on national security and particularly Benue state. In line with the objectives, the following questions will be formulated

1. What are the factors responsible for the recent conflict between herdsmen and farmers in Benue state?
2. What will be the impact of herdsmen and farmers conflict on national security?

Literature Review

A good number of researches have been carried out in Nigeria's North-central region that houses Benue state that will be the focus area of this research. The focus of this research will be on the impact of herders and farmers conflict on national security. The research will also give special attention to the strategies and efforts of various actors and stakeholders in putting an end to the enraging conflicts in the state. This chapter exposes review of relevant literatures that are important and related to this research. The literatures and theories that will be examined here will form the standard for the discussion of findings later in this work.

Theoretical Framework

According to Le Meur and Hachet (2010), theorizing herders-farmers conflict remains very difficult, since the actors, causes and dynamics are complex and varied. They believe that a combination of theories is needed to explain vividly herdsmen and farmers conflict escalation. Hence, this study will adopt a review of three fold-theoretical perspectives to discuss the issues relating to herdsmen and the farmers conflicts, to make for a more in-depth understanding of the variables. The 3 theories include, conflict theory, Eco-violence theory and the frustration Aggression theory. However, the study will be anchored on the conflict theory and the eco-violence theory.

Conflict theory will be adopted as part of the study's framework of analysis. Conflict theory explains the root of violence in any sector whether organized or not. The interdisciplinary field of conflict studies aims to explain all kinds of conflicts from local to international conflicts. The theory defines conflict generally as any state in which two or more social entities or parties perceived that they possess mutually

incompatible goals (Metch all, 1981). The theory also describes conflicts explicitly as sequences of interaction. Conflict theory will be singularly useful to explain herdsmen and farmers escalation generally.

The Eco-Violence Theory

This theory was developed by Homer-Dixon 1999. The theory seeks to explain the relationship between environmental factors and violent conflicts. Its basic assumption is that: Decrease in the quality and quantity of renewable resources access acts singularly or in various combinations to increase in scarcity, for certain population groups, of cropland, water, forests, and fish, thereby reducing economic productivity, both for the local groups expovincing the scarcity and for the larger regional national economies. The affected people may move or be forced for new areas, thereby causing ethnic conflicts when they migrate to new areas, while decrease in wealth, cause deprivation conflicts (Homer-Dixion, 1999).

Competition over scarce ecological resources has been aggravated in contemporary times owing to the impacts of climate change, which was exacerbated ecological scarcity across the world (Blench, 2004, Onuoha, 2007), thereby engendering violent conflicts. The eco-violence theory gives revelation to the nature and dynamics of the arable land, resource conflict and underdevelopment indices in Nigeria. The competition on arable land and the consequent conflicts become more intense amidst their ever reducing resources, herdsmen and farmers conflict and the present inefficient and ineffective policies on grazing by the Nigerian politicians.

The destruction of crops and cattle rustling are the two competitive reasons given by the agricultural farmers and the pastoralist herdsmen respectively for the increasing and incessant violent conflicts between them.

Conceptual Framework

Brief historical dimension of Benue state

Benue state is name after the Benue River and created from the Former Benue-Plateau state in 1976, along with Igala and some part of Kwara state. The state is located in the north central region of Nigeria, has a total population of 4,253,641 according to the 2006 census (National population commission, Bureau of statistics 2006, with an average population density of 99 persons per km². Benue state shares boundaries with five states, Nassarawa to the North, Taraba to the East, Cross-River to the South, Enugu to the South West and Kogi to the West. Male population is estimated at 2,144,043 and the female 2,109,598. The state has 23 local government areas. Benue state is largely known for its wide agricultural activities and nicknamed the "Food basket of the nation". The state has a collection of Christians and Muslims, its geographical coordinates all longitude 47^o and 10^o o' East. Latitude 6^o25', and 8^o,8' North,. Benue state is blessed with abundant mineral resources. These resources are distributed in the local government areas of the state. Among all the natural resources, only limestone and Kaolinite are exploited in commercial scale. Barite, Gypsum, Feldspar, Wolframite, Kaolinite, mineral salts and Gemstone, etc are the others.

Agriculture is the mainstay of the economy engaging over 75% of the farming population in the state. The state is also blessed with one of the longest stretches of river systems in Nigeria and this makes fishing a lucrative venture, while the water services the irrigation system for farming during the dry season and for the inland water highway.

Benue state with its capital at Makurdi is delineated into (3) senatorial districts and 23 local government areas.

The Concept of Herdsmen

Herdsmen or Herders are men who train breed and take of livestock, such as cow, cattle and earn their living by keeping such animal Iro (1994), posits that, herdsmen or pastoralist are nomadic or semi nomadic herders whose primary occupation is raising livestock. Traditional herdsmen engage in unorganized movement of herds while the semi nomads make transhumance movement and thereafter return to their camps or homes. Herdsmen are largely found in the Sahel and semi arid areas of west Africa, but as a result of climate change and desertification, many of them migrated further south into the savannah and tropical forests belt of West Africa. They are mostly seen in West African countries such as Nigeria, Niger, Senegal, Guinea, Gambia, Mauritania, Mali, Bukuna-Faso, Benin Republic, Cote'd'Ivoire and Cameroon. According to Toner (2002), the sale of cattle herd and dairy products such as milk constitute the primary source of income and livelihood of the herdsmen.

Concept of Farmers

Farmers comprise of women and men who engage in the cultivation of farmland and the planting of agricultural crops. The agriculturalist engages in the raising of living organisms for food and raw materials. Agriculture involves farming in all its branches as well as the cultivation and tillage of soil, harvesting of nay agricultural or horticultural commodities (Rileco, 1968). Agriculture is practiced for the purpose of providing food, clothes and shelter, and also for business or economic gains.

Herdsmen and Farmers Conflict

Herders and farmers, who usually had little and easily resolved disagreement are now involved in violent and fierce conflict in Nigeria and mostly the North-Central region. According to Asishava, (2017), the dangerous experience today in states like Benue, Niger, Nassarawa, Kogi, Plateau, Kwara and the FCT dates back to 2011, where the common feature across these states is the loss lives arising from the violent attacks by the Herdsmen.

A Human Rights Watch, 2013, showed that violence between the herdsmen and farmers in the villages have claimed the lives of over 3,000 persons since 2010. Attacks by the Fulani herdsmen as at 2014, had killed about 1,229 persons in the middle region of Nigeria comprising of Benue state, Nassarawa, Taraba and the southern part of Kaduna state. Between 2013 and second held of 2016, these states had experience the gruesome murder of over 5000 persons from about 100 communities. In one attack on Agatu Local Government Area of Benue state in 2016, over 300 persons were killed including children and women (Ihuah, 2017). There is also the movement of herdsmen from neighbouring countries, like Mali, Niger Republic, Chad and Cameroon into Nigeria through the northern boundaries down to the middle belt in search of grazing lands for their herds, Takaya, 2017.

The Concept of National Security

Generally, herdsmen and farmers conflicts disrupt and thereafter the sustainability of pastoral farming and crop production (Moritz, 2010). These clashes reinforced circles of extreme poverty and hunger, destroy social status, food security and condemn to high risk the lives of women and children of a teaching population like Nigeria.

National security therefore, deals with a situation where people live and go about their daily activities without any form of fears. It's a condition and state of peace and state of stable atmosphere, where people and properties are not destroyed. National security comprises of food security economic development and growth, political stability and generally human security. According to Robert-Okah, (2014), the farmers/herdsmen conflict has further worsened the security situations in the country. The security condition in Nigeria in recent times has become enormous and embarrassing to government. Nigeria in the recent period has experienced unprecedented level of insecurity. No wonder national security has become an issue for government, prompting huge allocation of the National budget to security (Robert-Okah, 2014). The emergence of herdsmen and farmers conflict and cattle rustling has compounded the national security challenges in the country. In the North-central and others of the north various and many communities are facing assortment of security challenges ranging from land disputes between herdsmen and farmers.

According to Imo, (2017), a lot of killings by the nomads and reprisal killings of nomads by the host communities happened during the conflicts. Herds of cattle belonging to nomads were also killed. This has practically reduced agricultural labour force in such areas which pose huge challenge to National security. At the time of the herdsman and farmers conflicts, there are reported cases of the trade and movement of small arms and light weapons, which according to Imo (2017), is inimical to the spirit of integration of Nigeria and peaceful co-existence. In Nigeria, the Boko Haram pandemonium predominantly in the North-East part of the country with the burdening case of militancy in the Niger-Delta and the new trend of cattle rustling and land disputes between herdsman and farmers, there is the increasing and significant undermining of Nigeria's national security. Moritz, (2010), avers that, Herdsmen/Farmers conflicts are complex products of both structures and processes and cannot be explained solely in terms of either. There have been at least 370 clashes involving herders and farmers in Nigeria in the last five years, compared to just 20 in the 15 years before (Idowu, 2017).

According to Tion & Terwase, (2018), the United States consider the Fulani herdsman as the second most dangerous group to Boko Haram in Nigeria, as the group in 2016 alone killed about 500 person in Benue state.

Empirical Review

With regards to the importance of herdsman and farmers conflict and national security, reasonable empirical studies have been carried out in different fields with different approached. While the menace continued notwithstanding, there is need for further study on the subject matter.

Dimelu, et al (2017) carried out a study on livelihood issues in herdsman-farmers conflict among farming communities in Kogi State, Nigeria. The study assessed the causes and effects of herdsman-farmers conflict on livelihood Nigerian communities in Kogi State. A total of 135 randomly selected crop farmers were used. Data were collected by use of structural interview and focus group discussion and analysis. The result showed that crop farmers were predominantly male (85.2%), married (85.9%) and with a mean age of 51 years. They were small side farmers with average of 2.9% and engaged in the production of yam(97.8%), cassava 92.6% maize 92.6% and other arable crops, mainly for income and household food supply. The farmers indicated that violation of laws/tradition; livelihood interference and cultural factors were the major causes of conflict between crop farmers and herdsman. Consequently, the socio-economic life, production outcome and settlement of crop farmers are affected, culminating to breakdown in livelihood assets of farmers. The study recommended strategic and regular orientation of resource users on the need for co-existence and adherence to regulations regarding use of resources and that multi-stakeholders efforts exploring grass not participation should be promoted by the government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in policies and strategies for management of conflict among others.

In his works Tersod, (2016) assessed the impact of farmers-Herder conflict on food security in Benue state. It adopted the theory of tragedy of the commons which states that when a resources in groups collective interest and thus ultimately destroys the resources. A survey design was used to obtain cross-sectional data through questionnaires, focused group discussions (FGDs) and oral interviews. A sample of 320 farmers was selected from the population affected by this conflict. The paper used descriptive statistical tools for analysis and found out that so many human lives were lost, farmlands, residents and schools were destroyed, leading to a decline in farm, output (causing food insecurity) and human capital loss. The study therefore recommend a strong governmental; policy in the localization of the pastoralists in line with the world best practices to avoid conflicts.

From the foregoing citation, it's implicitly obvious that the herdsman and farmers conflict in Nigeria is usually occasioned by migration of the herdsman from their original settlements in the far north down south middle belt as a result of climate change and desertification. The herders regularly moved to the north-central region blessed with arable land and pastures to provide grazing fields for their herds. This has actually mounted pressure on farmland, leaving the agricultural farmers with no option but to resist and fight to protect their lands for agricultural purposes which are the mainstay of their economy and

livelihood. This movement and grazing in farmlands regularly pitch the herders and farmers against each other resulting to destruction of lives and properties.

Blench (2010), in his serial work on natural resources in the North-central Nigeria, posits, among other things, the establishment of nexus between pastoral migration and increased herders / farmers conflicts in the ecological zone. This study blamed climate change, desertification and drought, land tenure system and scarcity, as well as, pastoral migration as factors that account for the spiral farmers / herder conflict in the region. This supports the dominant scholarly stand point on the subject matter.

The review robustly shows that, the herders and farmers had lived together in the far North of Nigeria. This age long co-habitation was never without disagreement, they actually had misunderstandings that were easily resolved without any serious implications. However, climate change manifesting in desertification and drought, explosion in the population of herders and the herders have pressured the herders out of their traditional settlement in the North-East and West of Nigeria to the North-Central region of Nigeria in search of grazing fields. The region prides of wetland and tropical rain forest very suitable for agriculture and pasture. The farmers in this region would stop at nothing in protecting their farmlands, crops and land which is their ancestral inheritance, the herders on the land, are ever ready for a dagger-war in so far as, they secure grazing pastures for their herds. The outcome of this is violent conflict, which is what we see in Benue State and the entire region.

This situation sadly, has resulted to war and destruction of lives and properties, untold hardship, poverty, economic desertification, displacement of the host communities and general hatred between the Fulani herdsmen and the farmers.

Factors responsible for the recent conflict between herdsmen and farmers in Benue state

The recent conflict between herdsmen and farmers in Benue State, Nigeria has been a major concern, resulting in the loss of lives, displacement of people, and economic devastation. This conflict has been exacerbated by various factors, which can be broadly categorized into environmental, social, economic, and political dimensions.

Environmental Factors

One of the primary causes of the conflict is environmental degradation (Ogundele, 2017). Climate change has led to a significant reduction in the number of grazing areas available to cattle in the Sahel region (IPCC, 2013). As a result, herders are forced to migrate to other areas, leading to conflict with farmers who compete for land and resources (Adediji, 2018). Additionally, the destruction of forests and grasslands through bushfires and overgrazing has exacerbated competition for resources (Ogunwumi, 2019).

Social Factors

Social factors also play a significant role in the conflict. The traditional way of life of herders and farmers is under threat, as urbanization and modernization have led to changes in land use patterns (Oladeji, 2017). The introduction of new technologies and farming practices has also led to an increase in crop yields, making farmland more valuable and increasing competition for it (Ejim, 2019). Furthermore, the social and cultural differences between herders and farmers have contributed to the conflict, with herders being perceived as foreigners who do not respect local customs and traditions (Ijere, 2018).

Economic Factors

Economic factors have also contributed to the conflict. The increasing value of land has led to a rise in land grabbing by herders and other groups, leading to displacement of farmers and herders (Akinlabi, 2018). The introduction of new economic opportunities has also led to an increase in the value of land, making it difficult for herders and farmers to access resources (Ogundare, 2020).

Political Factors

Political factors have also played a significant role in the conflict. The lack of effective governance and security has contributed to the inability of the government to effectively manage the conflict (Akinola, 2018). The failure of the government to address the root causes of the conflict has led to a lack of trust

between herders and farmers (Ejim, 2019). Furthermore, the politicization of the conflict by some groups has exacerbated tensions and made it difficult to find a solution (Ijere, 2018).

The impact of herdsmen and farmers conflict on national security

The escalating conflict between herdsmen and farmers in Benue State, Nigeria, poses a significant threat to national security, extending far beyond localized disputes to impact societal stability, economic prosperity, and overall governance. This conflict, often characterized by violent clashes and displacement, stems from complex issues, including competition for land and resources, exacerbated by climate change, population growth, and the failure of effective dispute resolution mechanisms. As the conflict intensifies, it undermines the fundamental principles of security, creating a dangerous cycle of violence and instability.

The first, and most immediate, impact of the herdsmen-farmer conflict is the erosion of the rule of law. The repeated attacks and retaliatory actions erode trust in the government's ability to protect its citizens and enforce justice. The inability of law enforcement agencies to effectively address the violence, and the perceived impunity of perpetrators, encourages further lawlessness and undermines the legitimacy of state institutions (Akinola, 2018). This erosion of trust can foster a climate of fear and insecurity, hindering economic activity and disrupting social cohesion.

Beyond the immediate violence, the conflict significantly hinders economic development. Agriculture is a cornerstone of the Nigerian economy, and the disruption of farming activities and livestock production due to insecurity has direct consequences for food security and livelihoods (Oladeji, 2017). The loss of crops, livestock, and agricultural land leads to reduced productivity, higher food prices, and potential food shortages. Furthermore, the displacement of populations and the disruption of trade routes further exacerbate economic hardship, creating a cycle of poverty and vulnerability that can fuel further instability.

The herdsmen-farmer conflict also contributes to social instability and societal divisions. These tensions exacerbate ethnic and religious tensions, especially in areas where the populations of herdsmen and farmers interact, further jeopardizing social harmony. The displacement of communities, coupled with the loss of lives and livelihoods, fuels resentment and animosity, making reconciliation and peaceful coexistence extremely difficult. This division within the community and across the nation contributes to a hostile and unsafe environment, undermining social stability.

In conclusion, the ongoing conflict between herdsmen and farmers in Benue State is not merely a localized issue but a significant threat to national security. It has a negative impact on the rule of law, disrupts economic activity, creates social instability, and poses a threat to overall national stability. Addressing this multifaceted challenge requires a comprehensive strategy that includes proactive governance, robust security measures, inclusive dialogue, and sustainable land management policies that address the root causes of conflict. Only through such a multifaceted approach can Nigeria hope to mitigate the devastating impact of this conflict and ensure long-term peace and security.

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